

Composite Culture in Medieval South India- A Vijayanagar Experience – 14th to 17th Century CE

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ABSTRACT

Composite culture is often seen in regions with a history of cultural diversity and intercultural exchange, such as trading centers, crossroads of civilizations, or areas with a history of migration and conquest. It is important to note that composite culture is not a static concept; it continues to evolve as societies and cultures interact and change over time. People of multi philosophical ideas had co-existed right from the Vedic period. At the end of Vedic times, we could notice the evolving and inclusive living of societies with Buddhist's, Mahavir's principles along with the Ajivikas to mention a few. With the beginning of Common Era, the principles of Christianity came into confluence and the followers of Islam also lived in the same society of south India when Islam originated. It goes without saying that the epigraphs are the primary and contemporary and more reliable source of the time and found mostly engraved on the stone walls of the temples. In this search we are lucky to have the multiple volumes of them published by The Indian Council for Historical Research (ICHR), categorically volumed on language basis. The specialty of Vijayanagar period is the availability of inscriptions in multiple languages like Tamil, Sanskrit, Telugu and Kannada.

Introduction:

Composite culture refers to a cultural phenomenon where multiple diverse elements from different cultural traditions come together to create a unique and integrated whole. This often occurs when different cultures interact, exchange ideas, practices, and values over time, leading to a blending and fusion of various cultural elements. Composite culture is characterized by its dynamic and evolving nature, as it reflects the ongoing process of cultural interaction and adaptation.

This blending of cultures can manifest in various aspects of society, including language, art, music, cuisine, clothing, religious practices, architecture, and more. In a composite culture, people from different backgrounds coexist and contribute to a shared cultural landscape, resulting in a rich tapestry of traditions that have been interwoven over generations.

Composite culture is often seen in regions with a history of cultural diversity and intercultural exchange, such as trading centers, crossroads of civilizations, or areas with a history of migration and conquest. It is important to note that composite culture is not a static concept; it continues to evolve as societies and cultures interact and change over time.

It also refers to the blending of two or more cultural influences. It is also known as syncretism. Acculturation, on the other hand, refers to the exchange of cultural features that results when groups of individuals having different cultures come into continuous contact; the original cultures may be altered, but the groups remain distinct.

In India, cultural synthesis is a prominent feature of its civilization. India is a melting pot of various cultures and religions, and it has been so for centuries. The country's diverse cultural heritage has been shaped by various historical events and influences, including the oncoming of Aryans, Greeks, Romans, Mughals, and British colonialism from north-west and the arrival of Arabs and China and South-East Asians through sea. The result is a unique blend of different cultures, traditions, and beliefs that have come together to form a rich and vibrant tapestry of Indian culture.

There are two important questions this paper tries to ponder as far as south India and Vijayanagar kingdom is concerned. 1st, Is multiculturalism new to medieval south India, and 2. How did the Vijayanagar society react to 'others', whether it was an inclusive policy or

exclusive. These two questions will logically arise an axillary query that Why Vijayanagar kingdom had become a choice.

As a prelude and to understand the response to the first question we may have a very brief look at the inclusive society that lived before the origin of Vijayanagar kingdom in 14th century CE.

South Indian Socio-Political and Cultural Scenario was completely different from its contemporary North India until the beginning of 14th century CE. Taking advantage of the two lengthy coastal lines the inhabitants had developed contacts with east and west even from ancient period. There has been thorough inter-mingling of people from many parts of the world like Greek, Rome, Arabian countries, South, South-East Asian countries, China and Japan. They carried on trade in both the directions of east and west and culture blended automatically and smoothly. The recent excavation reports and artifacts adds to the strength of this fact¹ that there existed a cosmopolitan life enjoyed by the society that was composed of members from many countries even before the birth of religions like Christianity and Islam.

When we look at the pages of history to know about the entry of Islam to then India and the reception of the same by the native society, there is much evidence, telling us about the early settlement of people from Arab countries in both the East and West coasts of south India. Scholars are of different opinions relating to the advent of Islam in India, but of course, most of them believe that Islam had first flourished on Malabar Coast and later spread to other parts of the sub-continent. Shaikh Zainuddin² the prolific scholar and the author of *Tuhafat-ul Mujahidin* (completed in 1583 CE), is of the view that the Muslims had first flourished on the Malabar Coast about the first half of the seventh century CE itself. Both Francis Day³ and Sturrock had gone further and corroborated this fact from their accounts. According to Sturrock, “from the seventh century onwards it is well known that Persian and

¹ Adichchanallur excavation-2004 and Kiladi Excavation Report, State Archaeology Department, Tamil Nadu, 2018, Chennai.

² Shaykh Zainuddin, *Tuhfatul-Mujahidin*, (Eng Trans) S.M.H. Nainar, Islamic Book Trust, Kuala Lumpur and Other Books, Calicut, 2006, pp. 28-38.

³ Francis Day, *The Land of the Perumals or Cochin Its Past and Its Present*, AES, Madras, 1990. p. 365.

Arab traders settled in large number at the different ports on the Western Coast of India and married the women of the country (south India) and these settlements were especially large and important in Malabar where from very early times it seems to have been the policy to afford every encouragement to the traders at the ports".⁴ On the other- hand the Arabs had maintained commercial contacts with the Coromandel Coast much before Islam came to India. Edkins⁵ corroborates that ancient Arabs had conducted commerce in greater esteem and exhibited great interest in developing overseas trade. During these days, the Arab merchants were regularly passing through the Coromandel Coast on their way to Ceylon, present Sri Lanka.

The early medieval Arab travelers signify Kayal Pattinam as the principal port of Maabar, which means 'passage' or 'ferry', that extended from Kulam (Quilion) to Nilawore (Nellore)⁶. Traders and missionaries from Mecca landed at Kayal Pattanam during the life time of Hasrat Abubakar, the first Khalifa of Islam, and the mosque built at that time⁷ was called as Kadarkarai Masudi and this Tamil word gives the meaning of 'Sea-shore Mosque'. Arabic coin of Hijri 71 (c. 693 A.D.) was found by Caldwell while his excavation conducted in 1860's at Kayal Patnam⁸.

Conclusion:

Tamil Copper plate dated in 875 CE⁹, in 232 A.H (854 A.D) tells us that a group of Muslim migrants started from a hillside village called Qarafatul Kubra near Muqattam in Egypt under the leadership of Muhammad Khilji, a descendant of Khalifa Abubackar arrived a spot on the seashore near modern Kayalpattinam, hence they named Kayalpattinam as Qahirapattinam who were patronized then by a Pandya King. The Tamil epigraphs of the Chola domain (850-1279 CE), that engulf more than 50% of the whole Indian epigraphy refer

⁴ Sturrock, *South Kanara*, Madras District Manuals, p.180.

⁵ Edkins, 'Ancient Navigation in Indian Ocean', JARAS, 1986, cited from Asadulla Khan, *History of The Arab Contact with Tamilagham from the Beginning up to 1400 A.D.*, The New College, Chennai, 2013, p. 17.

⁶ K.A. Nilakantasastri, *Pandyan Kingdom*, Swati Publication, Madras, 1972, p.169.

⁷ Abdul Latiff, *The Concise History of Kayalpatnam*, Shamsudeen Appa Publication, Kayalpattanam, 2004, pp.60-61

⁸ Bishop Caldwell, *A History of Tinnevelly*, AES, New Delhi, 1982. P-288.

⁹ Glossary of Tamil Inscriptions, vol-1,p-271,SII Vol-VII, 1038.

the followers of Islam or those who came from Arabian countries as *Sonakar* and *Yavandar*¹⁰. More over Y.Subbarayalu¹¹ has established beyond doubt that the trading body *Anjuvannam* and *Hanjuman* that occurs in various south Indian languages was comprised of the followers of Islam.

When the Pandya dynasty overcame the Chola power in south India, we could see that the Arabs had already entered royal service. We could see Sayyid Jamaluddin was the minister of Pandya King Sundara Pandi, in 1284 CE¹² indicates the level of acceptance of ‘others’ in important government service on one hand by the rulers and the whole society on the other hand. At this point of time, it’s necessary for us to remember that the Chola empire was no longer in existence and ended just five years before in 1279 CE. That indicates the level of confidence already gained by the Muslims and nature of their settlement in south India even before the arrival of Malik Kafur to Deccan. Rather these inferences should be viewed as a mirror of south Indian society where peaceful co-existence of multiculturalism prevailed since the beginning of the religion of Islam. As for as Christianity is concerned, it is generally considered to be as old as the religion itself on both the coastal regions of south India¹³. Hence, with the help of the above-mentioned instances we may conclude that composite culture was not a new phenomenon to the 14th century born Vijayanagar Kingdom in south India that clears us with our first question. With this understanding, now, let us proceed to the time period of the Vijayanagar empire’s scenario to resolve our second puzzle.

An attempt has been made to study through the sources like contemporary epigraphy, monuments and literature by observing varied aspects of society viz political alignments, military reforms, royal marriages, changes in the arrangements of the royal court, royal and public patronage and charity extended to deviated professionals which include traders, literature writers, foreign ambassadors, and privileges to common public, influence in dress etc.

¹⁰ For further reading view Y. Subbarayalu, *Studies In Cola History*, Surabhi Pathippakam, Chennai, 2001, pp-144-152

¹¹ Y.Subbarayalu, 2001

¹² Elliot and Dowson, *History of India Told by Its on Historians*, III, Low Price Publication, p. 24.

¹³ A.M. Mundadan, *History of Christianity in India*, Vol.1, *From the beginning up to the middle of Sixteenth Century*, (CHAI: Bangalore), 1989, 65-66

In the Ranganathaswamy temple at Srirangam, in the second circumambulating path (Prakara) in the eastern wall there is one inscription¹⁴ that records that Goppana, a general of King Kumara Kampana II, ruling as a viceroy from Cenji, after defeating the Thurukkar (Muslims) restored the idol to Srirangam. The record is dated in the Saka era 1293 which is equal to 1371 A.D. The earlier inscription that we find here, in Srirangam, just prior to Gopanna's belongs to 1317 A.D clearly showing a gap of fifty plus years indicating the period of the Madurai Sultanate. The focus has to be paid to the word referring to the Muslims as Thurukkar. Turuk is the name of the tribe to which the Delhi Sultans belonged to and this tribe had come from Afghanistan is a well-known fact in history, and only the tribe's name was mentioned that has been recorded but no indicator of any religious epithet has been used is worth mentioning here. There are many such inscriptions especially in Tamil inscriptions from different places and occasions that mention the Muslims after their tribe's name only¹⁵. Anyway, we are unable to understand the earlier names of Muslims, that were in practice during the times of Cholas viz *Sonakar* and *Yavanar* were also simultaneously used or not in the society. The term *Yavanar* is available even in Sangam literature (3rd century BC-3rd century CE) for all foreigners like Greeks, Romans and Arabs.

As we are aware that the Bahmani Sultans, Gajapati of Orissa (present Odisha) and Vijayanagar rulers were the contemporaries and major powers of Medieval Deccan and South India, there were continuous feuds between them which could be seen from the political history of the period. None among them were neither permanent enemies nor allies and they kept changing their sides very often. In this political situation it is true that religion could neither unite nor divide them. An epigraph reveals that the Gajapati ruler during one of the attacks on the Vijayanagar empire, destroyed the temples located in Usavadi, Padai Vidu and Valuthilampattu in 1463-64, which has been recorded in 1470 CE. This act was committed by Kapilendra, the Gajapati ruler according to the temple record on stone¹⁶. The epigraph throws light further to inform us that all the so caused destruction was overcome by the charity function of one Annamarasa, the executive agent functioned under the Vijayanagar king Narasimhan I¹⁷. Moreover, the medieval age is known for more wars and increased

¹⁴ SII vol-24, no-286, ARE 55 of 1892.

¹⁵ ARE 64b / 1916 pt. 2, para 33, ARE.119, 120 /1908.

¹⁶ Ibid, no-453

¹⁷ Ibid.

militarization. The above-mentioned feud from an epigraphy is only an example, otherwise it is quite a conspicuous fact for any reader of history that hardly religion had any place in politics.

The second fact is that the destruction of temples and loot in enemy land were carried out invariably by all rulers both of same faith or different faiths. In my opinion destruction of a temple and loot were not acts related to religion but a mode of communication and symbol of victory. Even the fate of Buddhist and Jain holy places was the same even in early medieval times. So, religion became a factor of politics in later periods only perhaps. Hence, we are to understand that the wars, destruction and loot were common features of war in medieval times and could not have hurt the public sentiments as they have been witnessing the same attitude of the rulers since ages. Thereby concluding that these political affairs failed to have any significant effect in their social life will not be far from fact.

Krishna Deva Raya who once defeated the Sultan of Bedar in a battle restored power and kingdom back to the Sultan and assumed the title *Yavana Rajya Sthapana Acharya* (founder of foreigners' rule). But this was not due to any-other reason except the political agenda. He used it as a strategy to subdue the sultans of Quli-Qutub-Shah of Golkonda and Raichur Sultan Ismail Adil Khan. This again proves beyond doubt that politics and religion were never amalgamated in this medieval period. The literary evidence also attest to the same fact.

We will elucidate a few facts of the incidents of the time in the political field. A combined effort of Gajapati of Orissa and Alludin, the Bahmani sultan is evident to conquer over the Muslim rulers of Malwa, Gujarat and Khandesh and as a result Gajapati gained certain territories of present Telangana. It is needless to stress that neither the Muslim nor the Hindu leaders took the line of religion for political gains. The war spoils in a battle against Vijayanagar was shared again between Gajapatis and Bahmani Sultans causing a big defeat to Devaraya II and then Kanchipuram was taken away by the Gajapatis from the kingdom of Vijayanagar. Thus, the political activities show a totally deviated direction from the view of the historians and show us the cultural mixing and peaceful co-existence of varied communities at the time of Vijayanagar.

Two famous Telugu literary works of this Vijayanagar period viz, *Rayavacakamu* and *Pratapa Rudra Caritamu* portray the three prevailing kings, the major powers viz Vijayanagara, Bhamani Sultans and Gajapatis equating them to the three Hindu gods, Brahma, Shiva and Vishnu. As we are aware from the time of Guptas (3rd-6th century CE) the rulers have been looked at as gods in the literature and epigraphs, no wonder the above-mentioned Telugu literatures of medieval time too, depict the kings as gods. But the more attractive part is that the Bhamani sultans who were of different religions were also seen as a Hindu god. These three rulers were shown as *Trimurti* of Hinduism vis Brahma, Vishnu and Shiva. Rather they have been described as *Narapati*, *Gajapati* and *Aswapati*. Vijayanagar rulers whose strength was seen in the infantry was called as *Narapati*, where in Sanskrit language *Nara* means human and *pathi/pati* is the ‘head’ or leader. While the Orissa kings had the strength of elephantry as their backing force known as *Gajapati* (*gaja*= elephant) and the Bhamani sultans who were renowned for cavalry as *Aswapatis* (*Aswam*=horse). This is how these three were equated to the *Trimurtis* of the Hindu religion. This pattern of identification in the literature reveals the level of composite culture of the society irrespective of their faiths. The high level of religious tolerance that prevailed in the time period of our study among the rulers and the public cutting across all the barriers is the remarkable feature of their cosmopolitan life which has to be noted and marked in bold letters.

Devaraya-II analyzed the secret behind the success of Bhamani Sultans’ military force as an able opponent leader and found their strength laid in mounted archers on the horseback. He appointed 10,000 *Turukshas* in his army. These mounted archers who were newly recruited were allotted free housing site lands besides the usual emoluments as a special remuneration for their ability and perhaps even as an attraction besides many other privileges¹⁸.

To read about inclusion of Muslims in the army in the words of Ferishta , “ Deo Roy upon this gave orders for the entertainment of mussulmans in his service, allotted them jaghires, (estates) erected a mosque for their use in the city of Beejanuggur, and commanded that no one should molest them in the exercise of their religion. He also ordered a Koraun (the holy book of the Muslims) to be placed before his throne, on a rich desk, that the mussulmans might perform the ceremony of obeisance in his presence, without sinning

¹⁸ E.I, vol-III, Sr-15, intro p-3.

against their laws. He also made all the Hindoo soldiers learn the discipline of the bow; in which he and his officers used such exertions, that he had at length two thousand mussulmans and sixty thousand Hindoos, well skilled in archery, besides eighty thousand horse and two hundred thousand feet, armed in the usual manner with pikes and lances¹⁹."

When Devaraya-II was reigning the Vijayanagar Empire in the 15th century, Abdur Razak from Persia, came as an ambassador to the kingdom of Bahmani Sultan by the Persian Sultan Shah Rukh to Bahmani kingdom. Having known about this, king Devaraya-II invited Abdur Razak as a royal guest to the Vijayanagar kingdom. Abdur Razak stayed in the Vijayanagar capital from April to December in 1443 CE and has left a detailed description of the kingdom to us.

The Hindu king Devaraya-II never looked Abdur Razak on the basis of his religion as a Muslim but was welcomed as an ambassador only. If the religious deviation was to that altitude which Robert Sewell felt so in 20th century while authoring the first book on Vijayanagara Empire as a forgotten empire, then this would not have been possible. It is necessary to understand that Devaraya II had no such compelling pressure on him so as to invite the ambassador of a rival neighbor ruler. Hence such instances give the real picture of the practical condition that prevailed in the medieval times.

An epigraph dated 1441-42²⁰, mentions one Ahmad Khan as engaged in the Vijayanagar army is not a rare inscription. Another foreign traveler, Domingo Paes from Portugal who visited Vijayanagar kingdom in around 1520, in his writings '*Chronica dos reis de Bisnaga*' (Chronicle of the Vijayanagar kings) details about the settlement of Moors and their service in Vijayanagar empire. He writes '...moors at the end of the city ...among them many were natives...paid by king and belonged to his guards²¹. In support of this idea that the Moors served as royal bodyguards, we have an incident in the regime of Krishnadeva Raya. In a conquest against the Sultan of Raichur, he had sent the troops led by the Moors as to lead the van²². Amur Khan who was in the royal service was granted a big estate for his

¹⁹ Robert Sewell, 'A Forgotten Empire', p-72.

²⁰ ARE 18/1904

²¹ Robert Sewell, A Forgotten Empire, London, 1900. p-256.

²² Ibid, p-329.

own maintenance by Ramaraya is another evidence²³ supporting the idea that Muslims were engaged in royal military service during the Vijayanagar period. Again, to reiterate the focus point that religion did hardly matter for anyone either the ruler or the ruled and the society was in general an inclusive society with people of different cultures and religion. In another instance, to speak about the level of understanding and amenity that prevailed in the society is from an epigraph that mentions a man professing Hinduism, though pious constructed a mosque for the *Turuksas* to offer prayers²⁴. Thus, from the top most point of the society down to the bottom level of a public many such instances are visible that gives us an insight into the society and public life of the time period.

Ainana-Malukka (Ain ul Mulk) was an important officer who requested for the charity of the welfare of the brahmanas to the ruler. The availability of an epigraph delivers the details of this charity recommendation²⁵. Accordingly, a village namely Bavanahalli was granted as charity to the brahmanas. This officer's political importance could easily be understood from the way he has been referred to as 'brother of the regent king'. Dil-u var Khan another well-known personality of the times of Rama Raya, who served as an agent of the ruler had gifted a village as Bhatta- Agrahara²⁶ to the brahmanas which should have been for the benefit of the *bhattas* who had served as teachers of higher education of course Vedic, and as assistance in judiciary as evident in the Chola times epigraphs²⁷.

While the Muslim officers were generous in promoting the brahmanical culture on one side, the Vijayanagar rulers on the other side, could be seen as promoters and believers of the *Dharga* culture of Muslims. A famous Babanatta was an astrologer of Vijayanagar times who due to his capability gained royal attention. We find the rulers attached much importance to his astrological fore-casts and thereby showed their largeness through charity. Venkatta-II, one of the Vijayanagara ruler was seen promoting Babanatta Dharga at Penukonda²⁸ by carrying out renovation work.

²³ Briggs, The Rise III, p-381.

²⁴ E.I, vol-4, kr-95.

²⁵ E.I Vol-XIV, p-210.

²⁶ E.C, Vol- X. KL- 147

²⁷ For further readings Vide S. Chandnibi, Bhattas as Teachers, *Journal of Indian History. And Culture*, Chennai, 2006, pp. 121-129.

²⁸ ARE 17/1910-11, Phara-59

The world of commerce is another important field where religious background never gained any attention at all in this period of our study even by the rulers cutting across the political borders of the day. In the time of Deva Raya II, T.V Mahalingam writes that he spent 28 years in fights with Bahmani Sultans. In such a horrible socio-politic conditions, there was one business magnet named Avachi Tippayya Setti who hailed from Nellore monopolized in the sea-trade, as informed by the literature of *Hari Vilasam* authored by Srinath in Hari Hara II's rule. This trader enjoyed good confidence with the then Vijayanagar ruler Hari Hara, Firoz-Shah the Bahmani Sultan and Kumaragiri Reddy of Kondavidu. Simultaneously he carried out trade successfully with all the three royal courts that makes it obvious of the fact that religion seldom had any role in public life. Such was the height of cultural-mixing that existed among the community at all levels.

There was no spirit of religion but cultural synthesis in this period. The Vijayanagar royal palace and court had dressed like that of Bhamani sultans. One example comes from the painting of Lepakshi temple showing the Vijayanagara court scene. The male members are seen wearing full sleeve shirts and conical long caps better known as *Kabayi* and *kullayi* locally (Figure-1 in the annexure). This was an act of acculturation from Bahmani Sultans by royals and nobles of Vijayanagar court which is also attested by Noboru Karashima, (OUP-2014)

As the focus of the paper is only Vijayanagar Empire nothing in the direction of cultural synthesis of the Bahmani Kingdom has been said about. Anyway it becomes necessary to write at least a few sentences to show how cultural blending was taking place in the Bahmani society simultaneously with that of Vijayanagar in the Deccan. Brahmins were appointed in the government offices and Feroz, the Bahmani sultan appointed them very extensively. He made Narasingh of Kerala as the peer of Bahmani kingdom²⁹ and also the first to take Hindu wives. In the tomb of Firoz one could see Perso-Bahmani arch supported by Hindu jambs on either side of the doorways, and the brackets supporting the *chhajja* remind one of the brackets in the Hindu temple of the Deccan.

In the field of politics in the Deccan of this time The Vemas of Kondaveedu and Velamas of Nalgonda were in constant feuds. Though both were only Hindus by faith,

²⁹ Sherwani H K, *Bahmanis of the Deccan*, pp- 144

Velamas became the allies of Bahmanis and Vemas sought the hands of the Vijayanagar and tried to settle their personal scores. To quote H.K. Sherwani ‘It will thus be seen that the religious sting which might be supposed to have existed between the Bahmani and Vijayanagar relations, was already dying out as some of the Reddys of the East were helping the Sultan against Vijayanagar, while the Raya of Vijayanagar was actually invading Telangana in much the same manner as he was marching into the Bahmani territory’³⁰. With due respect to Sherwani, the author wishes to differ that the religious sting was not dying but it was hardly present.

Coming to the field of architectural synthesis in Vijayanagar kingdom the Vijayanagara artists while sculpturing contemporary social themes various dance forms were one among others. Various dance forms like the stick-dance, (*kolattam*) musicians, also included ‘Central Asians dancers and European horse merchants’ (Karashima,2014) were also depicted in temple panels (Figure-2). Shanmugam P. says that Islamic influence found place in the buildings of Vijayanagar capitals of Hampi and Chandragiri too. He cites elephant stables at Hampi as an interesting model as that comprises several domes associated with multiple *sikhara*-type roofs. With regard to Lotus Mehal of the same place is one more striking example depicting the synthesis of the elements of both the cultures; ‘the tiered pyramidal roof of temple architecture and recessed and foliated arches similar to the Lodi tombs of Delhi. Same such a case could be seen in Chandragiri multi storied palaces known as Rani-Mehal and Raja-Mehal that consisted of pyramidal towers of the Hindu tradition along with arcaded facades with a series of Islamic arches. (Karashima, 2014)

The Bahmani architecture including mosques and tombs also adapted Hindu style in later times omitting the Delhi-Sultanate and Persian style, especially in the Jami Masjid at Daulatabad and the Deval Mosque at Bodan. The mosques also included Hindu style inscriptions and musical gallery too. (Karashima, 2014)

In conclusion we should understand that Robert Sewell the first to write about the ‘Forgotten Empire’ was a Civil Servant sent by The Imperial Britain to colonial India so with due respect to him for introducing us the Vijayanagar Kingdom, but at the same time we should be careful to understand his angle of writing was only to impress the colonial India

³⁰ Ibid

that there was nothing in their past except wars, loots, and destruction and only under imperial Britain Indians could experience peace and progress. So his imperialistic observation made him introduce words like foreigners, invasion, conquest, and claim as if Vijayanagara originated to save the religion. As we all are aware of their divide and rule policy it was necessary for the authors like Father Heras to view in religious angle.

The native Indian writers like Krishnaswamy Iyengar and TV Mahalingam with due respect we would consider them as historians of Nationalistic view. But the European writers moved for ahead of us and looked Vijayanagar history in a wide perspective like, trade and commerce, culture, architecture including state formation policies. Noboru Karashima and his team moved very neutrally in the late twentieth and early 21st century and laid a path for us.

Hence on their foot-prints the author wished to search and bring-forth the composite culture of Vijayanagar Kingdom touching various fields like political alliance, military reforms, induction of others in royal court and administration in varied positions, and created an inclusive society by cross cultural marriages, dress, food and adaption of other' s features in art and architecture.

Annexures

Figure-1, Painting of Lepakshi Temple showing full-sleeve shirts and long conical caps,
Source- Noboru Karashima.

Figure-2, Portuguese horse trader, Source-Noboru Karashima

Figure-3 Vijayanagar Kingdom 14th to 17th century CE, Source- Noboru Karashima

Figure-4 Panorama of the Battle of Talikota (1565). In the right panel, Husain Shah (riding a horse) orders the decapitation of Rama Raya (reigned 1542–65), the defeated ruler of Vijayanagara. *Ta'rif-i Husain Shahi* (Chronicle of Husain Shah). Source-Google